

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF KNOWLEDGE IN GEOGRAPHY LESSONS**Huseynova Tamara***Graduate student of Nakhchivan State University***Abstract**

Improving the quality of knowledge in geography classes is possible by effectively applying modern educational methods. It makes geography teaching interactive and interesting, increases students' motivation and makes the learning process more effective. Interactive maps, 3D images, websites and mobile applications help to improve the quality of geography knowledge. These apps provide practical examples and visual organization to help students better understand and remember geography concepts. These methods and experiences are an important tool for improving students' geography knowledge and motivation.

Keywords: modern education, interactive maps, concept, method, motivation, improving students' geography knowledge, 3D images.

In our educational activities, we see that today's children have very little motivation to learn and, especially, their interest in subjects that they initially consider simple, including geography, has decreased. High school students put geography in one of the last places among school subjects, because it is not as required when entering universities as other subjects. However, in the modern world, geographical knowledge is necessary for every person who considers himself successful, cultured and educated.

The reproductive teaching methods that were traditional in the recent past are no longer capable of developing the skills and abilities students will need in the new life conditions. The main focus is not on passively learning information or receiving it from a teacher, but on actively entering the problem, which requires independent creative efforts of the intellect. The teacher is required to master the art of organizing the active cognitive activity of students in the classroom, which is more interesting and at the same time more difficult than the usual communication of knowledge and checking their mastery.

How to increase students' interest in geography, and therefore the quality of their knowledge?

At the same time, modern pedagogical technologies become a powerful tool that enables the intensification of schoolchildren's mental activity, increasing their cognitive interest and, ultimately, every student's success in the process of studying geography. The introduction of non-traditional, developmental, active and modern forms of work helps to change the educational situation for the better.

Project-based learning technologies. When applying the technology of project activities to pedagogical practice, attention should be paid to the comprehensive development of the student's personality and certain goals should be implemented: identifying talented students; activation of the educational process; to develop students' interest in scientific work; develop public speaking skills; professional guidance for students; raising the level of scientific-methodical work. The results of project activities by students are reports, abstracts, essays, posters, etc. is carried out in the form.

Projects are presented in the form of presentations, which include various effects: sounds, photo and video

fragments. revitalizing the final submission process. In the project defense phase, students must present their project and answer questions from students. Students learn to debate, defend their work, present its strengths, defend their point of view, and listen to the opinions of the people around them. Working with projects facilitates the acquisition of geographical knowledge and develops skills in working with computer technologies. By using them, besides making students interested in the topic of the subject, they improve their knowledge and skills, instill interest and love for geography and science in general. The project defense process is a very good way to develop students' communication skills. The creative process that occurs when working on a project allows you to take a fresh look at the material and systematize your knowledge. Problem learning technology. One of the most important tasks of pedagogical science is the activation of the teaching process. The goal of the educational process today is to teach students to independently acquire new knowledge, to develop the ability to pose new problems and solve them independently. Creative activity becomes one of the main elements of the content of school education. Three main methods are used in problem-based learning: problem presentation, partial search, and research. The use of these methods is effective when the teacher sets a task for himself: to form qualitatively new methods of activity based on existing knowledge and skills - the ability of students to independently formulate and solve discovered or posed problems, the ability to make assumptions. and methods of testing them and planning experiments. Problem-based methods help the development of students' thinking in such a way that they can independently and quickly navigate the educational material, evaluate its importance, complexity and extent of application of acquired knowledge in relation to other knowledge. Problem-based learning methods help the development of creative abilities of each student at an individual level. The same question can be solved using different problem-based learning methods. The search and research method can be used in groups of students, most of whom have deep, solid knowledge of the subject. In strong groups, problematic situations in educational ac-

tivities lead to an increase in emotional upliftment, activity and interest in learning. In groups with mostly weak students, using more problematic questions and situations creates dissatisfaction, tension, and a negative attitude towards the lesson. It is not appropriate to refuse to use problem questions and situations in weak groups, because among such students there are boys who know the subject deeply and are interested in it. In this case, it is necessary to apply a differential approach to learning - multi-level questions, including problematic ones. The selection of training methods related to mental activity plays an important role.

Test technologies. In the geography course, there is a certain amount of basic knowledge and skills that form the basis of the future education of graduates. The effectiveness of any training process mainly depends on the comprehensive development of knowledge control methods. Knowledge control is necessary for any educational system and any organization of the educational process. It is a means of managing students' learning activities. But in addition to the test function, it is necessary to create certain conditions for the implementation of training functions, the most important of which is the objectivity of knowledge verification. The objectivity of the knowledge test implies the correct design of the questions, as a result of which there is an unambiguous opportunity to distinguish the right answer from the wrong one.

Game technologies. Recently, active forms of learning, including games, have been widely used in geography classes. Using games in teaching geography solves many problems. They develop cognitive interest in the subject, activate students' learning activities in the classroom and contribute to the development of the student's creative personality, since many of the games often contain the problematic nature of learning, as the initial question arises. can be answered, but the solutions are not clear. Many of the games provide opportunities for mutual learning because they include forms of group work and a consultation process. The use of games in the classroom is quite diverse. The teacher chooses all these game forms depending on the subject of the lesson, students' preparation, and their age. "Find your soul mate", "Speak up", "Investigation office", "Third wheel", "Travel in absentia", "Geographic dictates", "Trouble from the waist", "Travel agency between countries and continents", "Guess" and so on. [1, p.157]

Information and Communication Technologies. The main distinguishing feature of the use of ICT in geography lessons is the redistribution of information flows in the classroom. At the same time, the student becomes an active participant in the educational process. Active activity leads to a significant increase in motivation, and active search stimulates cognitive activity. Therefore, the teaching of geography using ICT should be considered as a new form of students' independent mastering of the content of the subject and organization of their development. Skills and abilities of research activity, orientation in information and its further processing are formed. The use of information technologies intensifies the transmission of information, greatly expands the illustrative material, and

creates problematic situations. The emotional background of learning is strengthened and students' learning motivation is formed. Information technologies differentiate and personalize the educational process; allows the teacher to significantly expand the volume of learned information and diversify the forms and methods of its perception by students. The use of computers, electronic maps, electronic textbooks and space photos in geography lessons allows to activate the cognitive activity of students, checking knowledge using electronic tests allows them to use different and methodical methods of working with a geographical map. important geographical skills-cartographic skills. This technology helps the development of the child's personality, increases the professional skills of the teacher, accelerates and enriches the learning process.

Working with the map. Maps are one of the main teaching tools in geography classes. The system of various tasks involving referring to the map allows creating conditions for the formation of students' cognitive activity at different levels: reproductive, partial search and research. For example, the reproductive level involves testing geographic nomenclature.

Creative works. Creative tasks I use include puzzles, crosswords, messages, reports, presentations, etc.

Technology of supporting records. Schemes teach to emphasize the main and most important things, teach to find and build logical connections, develop independent work skills, individual abilities, memory and logical thinking. When studying regional features, I practice making logic diagrams in class, which allows me to avoid too many words and teaches me to draw conclusions from the information received. For example, in 8th grade Climate, I use a reference diagram to help students explain how temperature, atmospheric pressure, wind, and precipitation are related. Special attention should be paid to explaining to schoolchildren the practical importance of geographical knowledge, the role of each person in everyday life and the economic activity of the entire population.

For example, knowledge about earthquakes and tsunamis - in which part of the world or in a country is possible, why they occur and how to behave during these natural disasters; knowledge about the inhabitants of the continents and oceans is very necessary to travel safely around the planet.

When studying atmospheric phenomena, we can pay attention to local signs of weather forecast

In the work experience of geography teachers, rich material has been collected to train schoolchildren for professions that require geography knowledge. The list of these professions is very extensive, from geologists, meteorologists, hydrologists to transport workers, trade workers, government officials and environmentalists. In almost every geography lesson, you can find a place to demonstrate the social importance of geographic knowledge and skills in modern life, to emphasize their social and cultural role in society, and at the same time to reveal the subjective importance of this subject knowledge for a person. [2, p.581]

Thus, the content of school geography, its integration potential with other subjects, serves as a good mo-

tivational basis for schoolchildren's learning in the transition to the second generation Federal State Education Standard.

One of the effective ways to eliminate educational failure and ensure the quality of education is a scientifically based system of using various pedagogical technologies.

References

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